

Reconsidering classroom space and language teaching and learning from a multimodal perspective

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ABSTRACT

In the English language classroom, many modes of communication beyond language, such as still images, moving images, and gestures, are commonly used, as are technologies such as blackboards and PowerPoint that enable different modes. This paper will argue that the role of modes and technologies in facilitating more communicative language teaching cannot be overlooked and that teachers need to consider their use of classroom space from a multimodal perspective. The paper explores classroom space and language teaching and learning through the example of a classroom in a public high school in Japan. It discusses how didactic, teacher-centred pedagogy tends to be promoted by traditional classroom spaces. It also outlines how modes and technologies can be used in the classroom space to mitigate teachers' power and fulfil students' needs and how consideration of the use of modes and technologies can contribute to teachers' professional development. The paper illustrates the significance of raising teachers' awareness of their use of semiotic modes and technologies in the classroom space to improve classroom language teaching and learning.

Keywords: English language teaching, multimodal perspectives, classroom space

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INTRODUCTION

More and more English teachers worldwide have been teaching communicatively in recent years. They focus on the use of language in context rather than just on the structure of language. They also allow students to interact and engage more in communicative activities (Harmer, 2015). In the Japanese context, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) emphasises communicative language teaching in the curriculum. For instance, the Japanese curriculum document MEXT (2018) states that English teachers should use English to facilitate authentic communication and should consider how to teach grammar effectively in meaningful contexts. However, attention to language alone does not necessarily lead to language teaching that is effectively communicative. This is because, as Iedema (2003) indicated, language relies on other semiotic modes. These are conceptualised as communication channels and resources for meaning-making (Bezemer, 2012). Textbooks utilise semiotic modes other than the language, including visual images, music, and colour. Likewise, in the classroom, teachers use a variety of semiotic modes such as position, gestures, and gaze. They also utilise semiotic technologies that support integrating semiotic modes into classroom teaching, such as blackboards, projectors, and PowerPoint. It is known that semiotic modes and the technologies associated with these influence teaching and learning in classrooms (Lim, 2021). Specifically, language teaching needs to be approached from a multimodal perspective that considers different modes of communication. In the next section, a classroom I taught in at a Japanese high school will be used as an example of considering classroom space and language teaching and learning from a multimodal perspective.

THE KBHS CLASSROOM

The classroom discussed below is at Kumagaya Boys High School (KBHS) in Saitama, Japan. The school was founded in 1895 and is one of the most traditional public high schools in Saitama Prefecture. There are about 40 students in the classroom, most of whom aim to take university entrance examinations to attend prestigious universities after graduation. I taught general English to students in Years 10-12 at this senior high school for five and a half years until 2022.

Figure 1 is a photograph of one of the English classrooms I taught at KBHS. The discussion of the space in this classroom will cover two aspects. The first is the physical layout of the classroom, including the features of each of the spaces within the classroom and how the classroom layout is shaped. Second, interaction

patterns and movements in the classroom are explored. The pedagogical implications for teachers' future practice are then discussed.

Figure 1. My English classroom at KBHS (KBHS, personal communication, December 22, 2023).

THE PHYSICAL LAYOUT OF THE CLASSROOM

The KBHS classroom has many elements in common with traditional classroom features, as Wright (2005) described. The primary features of the classroom layout are shown in colour in Figure 2, which also shows photographs of both the front and the back of the classroom.

The figure shows that students sit at individual desks in rows, facing the teacher, screen and blackboard. There are two small blackboards on the right and left of the main blackboard, which are typically filled with information about daily and weekly schedules for students. Therefore, these blackboards are not very useful for English teaching and learning, as it may be difficult for the teacher to write on

them. The screen is positioned in the centre of the main blackboard, occupying about one-third of the blackboard space. The projector is attached to the ceiling, so it is immovable. There is a teacher's desk and chair between the teacher and the students. The teacher usually places teaching materials such as a textbook, a CD player, and a Chromebook on the desk.

Figure 2. The analysis of the KBHS classroom layout (KBHS, personal communication, December 22, 2023).

There is a stage for the teacher where (s)he usually stands during the lesson. On the two sides of the classroom are windows and doors without visual displays. The classroom has a whiteboard at the back, but this only functions as a notice board for information such as scholarships and career education. For this reason, it is unusual for the teacher to write on the whiteboard in the English classes.

Lim (2021) categorises four different kinds of classroom spaces: Authoritative Space, Supervisory Space, Interactional Space, and Personal Space. In Figure 3, each of these kinds of spaces in the KBHS classroom is colour-coded.

Figure 3. Four spaces in the classroom. Based on Lim (2021).

The figure shows that the front centre position of the classroom is the Authoritative Space, where the teacher shows their authority. In the KBHS classroom, this space is distinctive due to the teacher's stage. The Supervisory Space indicates an area where the teacher moves between the students' desks. It includes the space behind students, defined by Lim (2021) as the Surveillance Space. In this space, the teacher can monitor learners effectively by making her/himself invisible. The Supervisory Space, including the Surveillance Space, expresses the teacher's power and authority because these spaces allow her/him to observe the students. The Interactional Space signifies a place where the teacher can offer personal advice to students. In this classroom, it overlaps with the

Supervisory Space (the Surveillance Space excluded). Lastly, the Personal Space is located behind the teacher's desk. There is an invisible wall between the teacher and students when the teacher stands there due to the furniture. In the KBHS classroom, the teacher's power is strengthened in the Personal Space because it overlaps with the Authoritative Space. Thus, each space in a classroom has different meanings and influences the relationship between the teacher and the students.

Classroom layout is affected and shaped by various external factors. Kress et al. (2005) and Jewitt (2006) provide some examples of these factors, such as government policies, examinations, local forces in the community in which the school is situated, history of the school, and school policy. Figure 4 shows the interactions between these factors. These factors explain how the KBHS classroom layout is shaped. For example, at the macro government policy level, the Japanese curriculum (MEXT, 2018) states that the teacher needs to effectively employ technologies such as audio-visual teaching materials and computers to enhance the quality of students' learning. Following this governmental policy, the Saitama Prefectural Board of Education installed projectors attached to the ceiling in all the classrooms in KBHS. The standardised university examination, which assesses the test taker's reading and listening skills and is taken by most KBHS students, may reinforce the traditional classroom layout. The examination facilitates individual work rather than communication and cooperation with peers because, for the exam, students need to be able to read and listen by themselves. At the meso level of the local community, the KBHS classroom can be influenced by graduates and residents who may expect the school to be disciplined and traditional. This expectation may make it difficult for the classroom design to change. At the micro level of the school, an influential factor is that students take many subjects a day in the same classroom. Therefore, keeping visual displays on the wall after class is unusual. The classroom space is complex due to these layered factors, and teachers need to pay attention to such factors to understand how their classroom spaces are shaped.

Figure 4. How external factors shape the classroom. Created based on Kress et al. (2005) and Jewitt (2006).

INTERACTION PATTERNS AND MOVEMENTS IN THE CLASSROOM

Interaction patterns between the teacher and students in the KBHS classroom can be didactic and authoritative. These patterns are reinforced by the traditional classroom layout in which students are individually seated facing the teacher, who is on the stage. The Authoritative and Personal Spaces where the teacher tends to teach also facilitate didactic and authoritative pedagogy. There are a range of factors that compel teachers to stay in these spaces. For instance, the fact that the two small blackboards and the whiteboard behind the students are not intended to be used in the English class can hinder the teacher from using the classroom dynamically. Students' backpacks in the Supervisory and Interactional Space also likely interrupt teacher movement. Moreover, technologies should not be overlooked as placing possible constraints on interaction patterns and teacher

movement. Lim (2021) explains that the whiteboard, which he calls a traditional semiotic technology, can be associated with formality since it keeps the teacher in the Authoritative Space. He also claims that PowerPoint limits flexibility, resulting in teachers' limited use of semiotic modes, less spontaneous feedback to learners, and less frequent unexpected lesson development. These characteristics of PowerPoint may result in students being less actively involved in the lesson. In the KBHS classroom, Chromebook restricts teacher movement and forces the teacher to stay in the Authoritative and Personal Space due to its connection to a projector via a cable and the fixed position of the screen. The characteristics and arrangement of semiotic technologies can increase teachers' prominence in the classroom and negatively affect interaction patterns. This contradicts the emphasis that the Japanese curriculum MEXT (2018) places on the need for English teachers to stimulate proactive, interactive, and authentic learning in their classrooms.

In the KBHS classroom, interaction patterns between students and students' movements can be more flexible than ones between the teacher and the students. Pair work is easily facilitated due to the students' proximity to each other. It is also facilitated by the current position of the projector on the ceiling, as the students can interact more freely with each other since the teacher no longer needs to place the projector between the students in the first and second rows (see Figure 5).

As Kress et al. (2005) indicated, the classroom layout can transform relationships among students and between the teacher and students. This also applies when students collaborate in groups by arranging desks together. In this communication pattern, students communicate autonomously while the teacher observes them in the Interactional Space. They can also attach posters, for example, butcher's paper, to the classroom walls to make a presentation (see Figure 6). In doing so, they circulate the classroom with roles as speakers and listeners. This can encourage students to feel a sense of ownership of the classroom, which is psychologically crucial (Wright, 2005). These examples show that the classroom layout can have transformative effects on interaction patterns between students and students' movements within the classroom space.

Figure 5. Installing the projector attached to the ceiling has transformed interaction patterns among students.

PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

Four pedagogical implications are suggested based on the preceding discussion of classroom space and language teaching and learning. First, English teachers' awareness of semiotic modes in the classroom needs to be raised to encourage language teaching that is more communicative and learner-centred. Authoritarian and didactic pedagogy often does not allow learners to show their interests or challenge norms (Jewitt, 2006), so teachers need to be able to consider ways of making their classrooms less teacher-centred. For example, English teachers can try to lessen power differences by teaching at each end of the Authoritative Space rather than in the centre (Lim, 2021). Standing in the off-centre position can lead to less frequent use of the Personal Space in a classroom like the one in KBHS. The introduction of technologies such as a wireless presentation clicker also enables teachers to move and even teach in Supervisory and Interactional Spaces. Although Supervisory Space reinforces the teacher's power, as mentioned above, the dynamics of teacher movement can arguably be increased through this space. The teacher can also utilise the Interactional Space to provide students with more individualised attention, for example, by squatting down and speaking at the eye

level of learners. In doing so, it becomes easier to provide formative and individual feedback. Some semiotic modes and technologies discourage authoritarian and didactic pedagogy, whilst others facilitate such pedagogy as discussed in the previous sections. Teachers should strive for so-called structured informality – a relationship between teachers and students in which a harmonious learning environment and classroom rapport are achieved, thereby minimising hierarchical power relationships (Lim, 2021). English teachers need to consider how to use semiotic resources to achieve structured informality in their classrooms.

Figure 6 Students put butcher's paper on the wall to make a presentation (KBHS, personal communication, December 22, 2023).

Second, PowerPoint is so commonly employed in the classroom that teachers should consider its benefits and drawbacks deeply. While it can facilitate effective learning for students, specifically in conveying ideational and textual meanings, it also promotes teacher-centred pedagogy that transmits information from the teacher to students (Lim, 2021). Therefore, it is vital that teachers consciously allocate some time for students to learn inductively and to discuss open-ended questions. Also, concerning the classroom layout, if the screen used to display PowerPoint occupies the entire blackboard or whiteboard, there is no space for teachers to write freely. In this case, an additional blackboard or whiteboard could

be installed. Lim (2021) pointed out that using a board can allow the teacher and students to form knowledge together.

Third, the dynamic utilisation of the classroom can assist the teacher in accommodating students' different learning styles (see Kress et al., 2005) and encourage students to take advantage of various language learning strategies. For instance, among strategies outlined by Dörnyei and Ryan (2015), group presentations in which butcher's paper is used to retell a story can provide an opportunity for learners to effectively use cognitive strategies, such as summarising and using images, along with social strategies such as collaboration with classmates.

Lastly, attention to semiotic modes beyond language can contribute to the professional development of English language teachers. In particular, considering semiotic modes before and after a lesson improves teaching skills. While teachers usually plan what and how to teach when preparing for a lesson, they should also consider their positioning and movement by incorporating these semiotic modes into the lesson plan. For instance, when modelling pronunciation, teachers should plan to stand in the centre of the classroom to be visible and audible. When monitoring, the teacher can instead move unobtrusively throughout the classroom. It is also crucial to carefully consider the teacher's positioning and movement if any student has hearing problems (Scrivener, 2012). Detailed preparation of a lesson in terms of these semiotic modes, rather than teaching on an ad hoc basis, enables teachers to teach more effectively. Moreover, increasing awareness of these modes enables teachers to reflect on their practices. It is worthwhile to record a lesson to analyse it in terms of space and positioning. In particular, teachers should reflect on how they use the Authoritative Space because, as Scrivener (2012) explains, by avoiding the space, they can implicitly convey to students that the teacher does not necessarily play the leading role in the lesson. Such reflection allows teachers to consider how to best utilise semiotic modes to create structured informality. Paying ample attention to semiotic modes before and after teaching, they will be able to make English classes more student-centred.

CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed classroom space and language teaching and learning from a multimodal perspective through the example of a KBHS classroom. It has shown that, due to the traditional classroom layout and technologies, the teacher tends to teach in the Authoritative and Personal Spaces. Consequently, the

pedagogy may be didactic, authoritarian, and teacher-centred. However, developing teachers' understanding of the benefits and drawbacks of semiotic modes and technologies can help redress power imbalances in the classroom. English teachers are encouraged to consider how they can create structured informality through an understanding of the features of each semiotic resource in their classroom. Reflection – before and after lessons – on using semiotic resources should not be overlooked in teacher professional development.

This paper has shed light on the significance of aspects other than language in the English language classroom. While semiotic modes and technologies are commonly used in the classroom worldwide, it is doubtful whether ample attention has been paid to them. English teachers need to further increase their awareness of a wide range of semiotic modes and technologies because, as Jewitt et al. (2016) emphasise, it is crucial to examine all semiotic resources to study meaning. A multimodal perspective enables teachers to reflect on and develop teaching and learning in their classrooms.

AUTHOR

Shogo Yamamoto is a teacher at Kumagaya Boys High School, Saitama, Japan. He is interested in the role of technology and multimodality in harnessing learning and teaching capacity and embracing the classroom teaching environment.

REFERENCES

- Bezemer, J. (2012, March 16). "What is a mode?" [video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kJ2gzOQHhI&t=3s&ab_channel=JeffBezemer
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ryan, S. (2015). *The psychology of the language learner revisited*. Routledge.
- Harmer, J. (2015). *The practice of English language teaching*. Pearson Education Limited.
- Iedema, R. (2003). Multimodality, resemiotization: extending the analysis of discourse as multi-semiotic practice. *Visual communication*, 2(1), 29–57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470357203002001751>

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- Jewitt, C. (2006). *Technology, Literacy, Learning: A Multimodal Approach*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203964101>
- Jewitt, C., Bezemer, J., & O'Halloran, K. (2016). *Introducing multimodality*. Routledge.
- Kress, G., Jewitt, C., Bourne, J., Franks, A., Hardcastle, J., Jones, K., & Reid, E. (2005). *English in urban classrooms: A multimodal perspective on teaching and learning*. RoutledgeFalmer.
- Lim, F. V. (2021). *Designing learning with embodied teaching: perspectives from multimodality*. Routledge.
- Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT). (2018). *Koutou gakkou gakushuu shidou youryou gaikokugo (eiyaku)* [the course of study for the foreign language class in high school]. https://www.mext.go.jp/content/20230328-mxt_kyoiku02_100014466_001.pdf
- Scrivener, J. (2012). *Classroom management techniques*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, T. (2005). *Classroom management in language education*. Palgrave Macmillan.